

PRODUCTIVITY IN PROFESSIONAL TOURIST GUIDES: A SCALE DEVELOPMENT STUDY WITH MIXED-METHODS SEQUENTIAL EXPLORATORY DESIGN

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Abstract

Tour guides have been described as being critical in the design and delivery of the tourism experience. It is obvious that the development of the field of tourist guidance, which is of the key players in the tourism sector and giving it the importance it deserves should be done in the light of academic studies in this field. The purpose of this study is specific to professional tourist guides productivity is to develop a perception scale. In the research, the exploratory sequential mixed method was adopted and acted with the idea of creating an original and native scale. Within the scope of this method, the qualitative stage was performed first and then the quantitative stage. The discovery of the perception of efficiency of professional tourist guides made the study original. It was written with the idea of filling such a gap in the literature and increasing the research to be conducted in the field of scale development for professional tourist guides.

Keywords: Professional Tourist Guide; Productivity; Scale Development; Mixed Method.

PRODUTIVIDADE EM GUIAS TURÍSTICOS PROFISSIONAIS: UM ESTUDO DE DESENVOLVIMENTO EM ESCALA COM DESENHO EXPLORATÓRIO SEQUENCIAL DE MÉTODOS MISTOS

Resumo

Os guias turísticos têm sido descritos como sendo fundamentais na concepção e entrega da experiência turística. É óbvio que o desenvolvimento da área da orientação turística, que é um dos principais intervenientes no setor do turismo, e dar-lhe a importância que merece, deve ser feito à luz de estudos acadêmicos nesta área. O objetivo deste estudo específico da produtividade dos guias turísticos profissionais é desenvolver uma escala de percepção. Na pesquisa foi adotado o método exploratório sequencial misto e atuou com a ideia de criar uma escala original e nativa. No âmbito deste método, foi realizada primeiro a etapa qualitativa e depois a quantitativa. A descoberta da percepção de eficiência dos guias turísticos profissionais tornou o estudo original. Ele foi escrito com o intuito de preencher tal lacuna na literatura e aumentar as pesquisas a serem realizadas no campo do desenvolvimento de escala para guias turísticos profissionais.

Palavras-chave: Guia Turístico Profissional. Produtividade. Desenvolvimento de escala. Método Misto.

PRODUCTIVIDAD EN GUÍAS TURÍSTICOS PROFESIONALES: UN ESTUDIO DE DESARROLLO A ESCALA CON DISEÑO EXPLORATORIO SECUENCIAL DE MÉTODOS MIXTOS

Resumen

Los guías turísticos han sido descritos como críticos en el diseño y entrega de la experiencia turística. Es obvio que el desarrollo del campo de la orientación turística, que es uno de los actores clave en el sector turístico, y darle la importancia que merece debe hacerse a la luz de los estudios académicos en este campo. El propósito de este estudio específico de la productividad de los guías turísticos profesionales es desarrollar una escala de percepción. En la investigación se adoptó el método exploratorio secuencial mixto y se actuó con la idea de crear una escala original y nativa. En el marco de este método, primero se realizó la etapa cualitativa y luego la etapa cuantitativa. El descubrimiento de la percepción de eficiencia de los guías turísticos profesionales hizo que el estudio fuera original. Fue escrito con la idea de llenar ese vacío en la literatura y aumentar la investigación a realizar en el campo del desarrollo a escala de los guías turísticos profesionales.

Palabras clave: Guía Turístico Profesional. Productividad. Desarrollo de escala. Método Mixto.

1 INTRODUCTION

Tourism is a major economic activity on a global scale (Przybyszewski et al., 2017). Tourist guides are an important profession in the tourism industry. They are, without a doubt, professional tourist guides who spend a significant amount of time interacting with tourists who are travelling to see diverse cultures. Tourist professionals who interact and influence visitors often are known as tour guides.

The tourist guide's personality will incorporate impressions of the nation and its perception. The tourist guide's expertise, abilities, and behaviour will also have a significant impact on how satisfied visitors are after they leave the country (Akmel, 1992). In light of this, a tourist guide should be well-versed in the geography and reality of the nation as well as being knowledgeable, self-assured, and modern.

Tourist guides are volunteer tourism ambassadors. (Değirmencioğlu, 2001). Guides should also be skilled interpreters, storytellers and intercultural communicators. In order for cultural mediation to be implemented correctly and fully, guides should develop intercultural communication skills from the beginning of vocational training (Saraiva & Anjos, 2019).

Since the professional tourist guide assumes the position of chairman, s/he is the group's leader and must adhere to their needs. Because the knowledgeable tourist guide is in charge of everything that directly or indirectly affects the tourist group. The expert tourist guide must first embrace the tourist group in order to meet to their demands.

S/he should come to feel like a member of the group by communicating with them and interacting with them. As a result, there is mutual trust between the leader and the followers (Polat, 2001).

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In addition to the skills and responsibilities that a professional tour guide has, in order to carry out his job well, the possibilities provided by the travel agency to which s/he is connected, the attitudes and methods of other firms or individuals with whom s/he works, are also crucial. From this vantage point, a variety of factors influence how effective licensed tour guides are. Bayram and Zengin (2017) discussed and examined the psychological factors affecting the productivity of tourist guides as stress, mobbing, job satisfaction and motivation.

The purpose of this scale development project is to investigate how professional tour guides evaluate their job efficiency and to determine the factors that impact it. The exploratory sequential mixed approach was used in the study with the goal of developing a unique and local scale. As a result, this research is regarded crucial in order to close the gap in the national literature, advance the area of scale development for professional tour guides, and provide guidance for academics interested in exploring professional tour guide productivity.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Tour guides have been described as being critical in the design and delivery of the tourism experience. Scholars have examined the role of mentors more as communicators and experience brokers. (Mason & Christie, 2003; Randall & Rollins, 2009; Weiler & Black, 2014; Weiler & Walker, 2014). Weiler and Black (2015) stated that tour guides co-create tourism experiences by mediating in four categories: (1) physical access; (2) understanding (intellectual access); (3) encounters (interactions); and (4) empathy (emotional access). Recent research on adventure tourism and wildlife tourism has supported these mediation areas as key dimensions of experience quality in guided tours (Houge Mackenzie & Kerr, 2014; Borges de Lima & Green, 2017).

This evolution from one-way communication to interactive and responsive guidance has been summarized by Raikkönen (2014, p. 95): "Tour leaders should be seen as experience providers whose task is not to impose ready-made experiences but to focus on consumers and consumers, they must be seen as experience providers to experience everything they experience. strengthen it." In this context, it is emphasized that the tourist guide is seen and supported as an experience provider.

While Hacıoğlu (1989) identifies the tourist guide as the first person in charge of the trip, Usta (1992) describes him as a travel companion, Çimrin (1995) as a person who gives connections, and İçöz (1996) as a person who solves any difficulty. Dahles (2002), on the other hand, presented the tourist guide as a welcoming ambassador, and Poria et al. (2006) as a fountain of information.

As a matter of fact, these expressions are kind of keywords that evoke the profession of tourist guide. When tourist guides are examined within the framework of these keywords, the tour carried out by the guide is actually a group. The members of this group consist of tourists participating in the tour, the group dynamism takes place during the tour, in some ways it also shows the characteristics of a formal group, it can also be defined as a temporary organization formed by people to achieve a

purpose in a certain time period, such as an organization without a place.

Cohen (1985) mentioned that there are two exit lines in modern tourist guidance and he stated that these exit lines are way-finding/guidance and mentoring. According to him, the leadership and intermediate roles of a tour guide are made up of four basic elements, which are, respectively, instrumental, social, interactional, and communicative characteristics.

The purpose of the guide, according to Cohen (1985), is to create tourist destinations at the marginal periphery of the ecological tourism system. In this context, there are geographical guides who take visitors to new places they haven't before visited and experienced. This category of tour operators offers services outside of urban areas, such as in valleys and mountains.

Professional tourist guides have many roles, such as leadership and intermediary, as well as advisor, informant, translator, consultant, instructor, and mediator. The guide who implements these roles well is directly effective in the positive or negative conclusion of the touristic experience (Türkmen, 2017, p. 913).

In many studies on guiding roles, it can be said that key roles focus on leadership and mediation. In this respect, Güzel and Köroğlu (2014) determined that there is such an effect as a result of their research to determine whether the leadership and intermediary roles of the guides have an effect on the performance and tour experience. For this reason, a professional tourist guide must first and foremost possess strong leadership and organizational skills.

Figure 1. Tour Leader Guiding Styles

Source: Tsaur & Teng (2017).

From the point of view of the tour leader roles studied, tour leaders exhibit consistent behaviors and models to successfully play various roles. Tsaur and Teng (2017) summarized the 12 tour leader guidance styles above: constant reminder, fully prepared, witty, empathetic, giving priority to members, cultural ambassador, meaningful, attentive, quick-witted, responsible, thoughtful and customer-oriented.

The main value of this study comes from the roles played by tour leaders, which allows exploring leadership styles from the perspective of how tour leaders successfully play different roles. In addition to the qualifications and roles that a professional tourist guide has in performing his/her profession effectively, the opportunities offered by the travel

agency s/he is affiliated with, the attitudes and approaches of other businesses or individuals with whom s/he is in cooperation with the guide are also important (Kumar, 2021, p. 2; Nikolskaya et al., 2022, p.1).

From this point of view, there are many factors that affect the efficiency of professional tourist guides. Bayram and Zengin (2017) discussed and examined the psychological factors affecting the productivity of tourist guides as stress, mobbing, job satisfaction and motivation. From the point of view of contemporary tourism, tourist guide is the only profession recognized and regulated by law in the tourism trade and has an important role in operationalizing travel programs in practice and facilitating and mediating between destination elements (Meira et al., 2018).

According to the literature has been determined that studies on professional tourist guides and their work efficiency are limited in number and mostly theoretical. The lack of a domestic, original scale to measure the perceptions of professional tourist guides towards work efficiency, and the development of a productivity perception scale (PTG productivity perception scale) in professional tourist guides was deemed necessary for the research to fill the gap in this area. The fundamental issue of the research is whether the 'Professional tourist guides productivity perception scale' produced by the researcher is a valid and trustworthy scale.

3 METHODOLOGY

The method section first explains the methodological approaches used in the research method, the philosophy of the research, the causality of the scale development study, the exploratory sequential design as a mixed method research, and the reason for preference, followed by a staged presentation of the applied qualitative research design and quantitative research design.

The mixed method research adopted "n th' study is defined as research that allows to see the whole picture or as a research in which quantitative and qualitative methods are used in the same research, data are collected and analysed, the findings are integrated, and prospective predictions are made (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2007; Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007).

The mixed method, which emerged as a third research paradigm, helps to establish a bridge between qualitative and quantitative methods (Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2004). Thanks to the mixed method, multiple methods have begun to be preferred instead of a single study in which a single qualitative or quantitative study is collected, which is translated as a single study. According to Cresswell (2006), the basic premise of the mixed approach is that "using quantitative and qualitative approaches together provides a better understanding of research problems than using either approach alone".

Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2014), on the other hand, stated that the basic principle of the mixed research method is that the researcher should obtain multiple data by making use of different strategies, methods and approaches. mixed methods research is based on pragmatist philosophy (Cresswell & Plano Clark, 2007; Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003) and transformational perspective (Greene, 2007; Mertens, 2009).

This research is a mixed method in which qualitative and quantitative research methods are applied together it is modeled using. The mixed method design used in this research is according to Christensen, Johnson and Turner (2014), the qualitative part is named first, then the quantitative part due to its preparation, the sequential pattern is also named by Creswell (2005) as the discoverer sequential the pattern is equal status as the paradigm emphasis of Christensen, Johnson and Turner (2014).The figure of the exploratory sequential pattern is presented below.

Figure 2. Exploratory sequential mixed methods research design.

Source: Park et al. (2024).

This research was modelled using a mixed method in which qualitative and quantitative research methods were applied together. The mixed method design used in this study is sequential design, as Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2014) named the qualitative part and then the quantitative part, and the exploratory sequential design, as Creswell (2005), named after Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2014) as the paradigm emphasis, equal status was preferred.

In the study, which was started with the aim of developing an original scale, answers were sought to the questions of how to become an efficient tourist guide, how to become an efficient tourist guide, what are the factors affecting the efficiency of a tourist guide, is the developed scale a valid and reliable scale.

3.1 Qualitative Method

The qualitative data of the study were obtained by using a semi-structured interview form. In the semi-structured interview form, firstly, after the theoretical framework was created, the literature was reviewed, and the opinions of two professional tourist guides and two academician experts selected in the pilot interviews were prepared in the form of 8 questions.

3.1.1 Qualitative Participant Selection

Snowball or chain sampling technique, one of the purposive sampling methods used in qualitative research, was used in the research. Who can be the most knowledgeable about the process? Who would you suggest I start with and talk to about it? (Patton, 1987, p. 56). In addition, this chosen method is effective in identifying individuals or situations that can be a rich source of information regarding the researcher's problem (Yıldırım and Şimşek, 2016, p. 122). For this purpose, a total of 11 professional tourist guides were interviewed by snowball sampling.

3.1.2 Qualitative Data Collection Procedure

The study's qualitative data were collected utilizing a semi-structured interview form. After developing the theoretical framework, the literature was reviewed, and the opinions of two professional tourist guides and two academic experts selected in pilot interviews were solicited concerning the semi-structured interview form.

3.1.3 Qualitative Data Analysis

The data research analysis followed the five-stage method proposed by Schloss and Smith (1999) and developed by Erdoğan and Ok (2009), as it follows: 1) transcription of the interviews, 2) reliability analysis, 3) coding of the data, 4) creation of themes and 5) categories, results and comments.

3.2 Quantitative Method

3.2.1 Quantitative Participants

The universe of the research consists of 9840 professional tourist guides with national action, affiliated to the chambers of the Turkish Tourist Guiding Association. When the part selected from the population, namely the sample, was formulated and calculated to collect information, it was found to be 264 people with 90% confidence level and 370 people with 95% confidence level (Raosoft, 2021).

3.2.2 Quantitative Data Collection Procedure

To measure the productivity perception of professional tourist guides, the survey technique was adopted as the most preferred data collection tool in quantitative research. Due to the continuation of the global epidemic in our country and all over the world and the restrictions on going out, the surveys were prepared online. As seen above, the applied questionnaire consists of two parts. In the first part, it was asked to answer questions about the demographic characteristics of professional tourist guides.

To this end; gender, marital status, age and working style were asked. In the second part, the 30-item question prepared by taking the opinions of experts on developing a PTR productivity measurement tool was prepared by adopting a 5-point Likert scale (1: I strongly disagree, 5: I strongly agree) and they were asked to answer. In determining the number of item questions to be answered, it was taken as a basis to prepare three times the number of items designed to be used in the scale based on scale development studies (Tezbaşaran, 2008).

3.2.3 Quantitative Data Analysis

SAS 9.4 program was used for the statistical analysis of the data in the research. First, it was understood that the data showed normal distribution as a result of the Shapiro-Wilk test, and then parametric tests were applied in statistical analysis. In pairwise comparisons between two-category variables, t-test was used, and Analysis of Variance (F-test)

was used to reveal the differences between variables with three or more categories.

Correlation analysis was used to reveal the relationship between dependent variables. The factor structure of the scale developed by using explanatory factor analysis was tried to be determined, Principal Components Analysis and Varimax Rotation method were used. Akaike's Information Criteria (AIC) and Schwarz Bayesian Information Criteria (SIC) were examined on the factors. The internal consistency of the scale was determined by the Cronbach's alpha coefficient. A value of 0.05 was accepted as the level of significance in the entire study.

4 RESULTS ANALYSIS

4.1 Qualitative Results

When the demographic findings of 11 professional tourist guides participating in the qualitative research were examined, it was seen that there were 9 male and 2 female participants according to gender. On the other hand, in terms of age groups, the youngest of the participants is 29 years old and the oldest is 60 years old. There are professional tourist guides with a minimum of 6 years of professional experience and a maximum of 20 years. Participants were coded from K1 to K11.

When Table 1 is examined, it is seen that the productivity perceptions of professional tourist guides consist of four sub-themes: (a) job satisfaction and job security, (b) group characteristics, (c) tour programs and (d) professional cooperation. (a) Job satisfaction and job security, "having the opportunity to work independently" (f=5), "the profession does not have the position it deserves in society" (f=10), "the profession does not provide a guaranteed future" (f=9), "having giving the chance to do something with the skills one has" (f=3), "difficulty of working conditions" (f=11), "agency compliance" (2), "the region's readiness for tourism" (f=3), "the job is short-term and different searches due to irregularity" (f=5), "decreased love and desire for the profession in an insecure environment" (f=3). Opinions chosen for the sub-theme codes of 'difficulty of working circumstances' and 'the profession is not in the position it merits in society' are as follows:

"We can say that we are putting our heads in the lion's mouth, so to speak, although there is no great danger when we say putting our head in the lion's mouth, we are constantly on the road and the control of the vehicle is not in your control, so safety is a bit of a question mark because it is a system that is out of your control, there is nothing you can do in case of a sudden accident." K3

"Health is of course indispensable, but let's not forget that many guides do not have social security. Because they find short-term and irregular jobs (except agency employees). From a professional point of view, the above-mentioned concerns affect productivity negatively from time to time." K2

"Professional tourist guides need to defend their rights and increase the awareness that the profession deserves in the society. The fact that the profession is in such a position creates negative effects. In an

insecure environment, the love and desire for the profession also decreases and it brings along different job searches." K1

(b) Group characteristics, "education/cultural level of the group" (f=7), "socio-economic status of the group" (f=6), "intention to participate in the tour" (f=3), "homogeneity/heterogeneity of the group" (f=1), "sharing with the group, ensuring harmony and acting together" (f=4), "providing dominance of the group" f=2, "meeting the needs of the group" (f=1), "meeting the expectations of the group" (f=5) was coded as "the group's satisfaction with the round" (f=10). The selected opinions regarding this sub-theme are as follows;

"In terms of guidelines, productivity may be described in two ways: 1) customer satisfaction centered, 2) customer sales motivated.... A well-trained guide in these areas will, of course, boost client happiness and sales performance. When there is harmony in certain groups, especially when the level of education is high, sharing and collaborating increases efficiency." K2

"Guiding persons from poor cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds affects my efficiency. While detailed explanations and talks boost desire, drive, and productivity, you transmit basic and shallow information to those with minimal understanding, which becomes tedious." K1

"The reason the group joined the tour is also important. For example, does a group you go on a cultural tour come to learn or just to spend the day? In short, we do what they want. If there are people who come for culture, we prepare accordingly." K9

"Of course, the cultural level and economic level of the group affect productivity... What the other party expects is important. What does he want, why did he buy this tour? We welcome people who come, serve

them, and pass on the information we have to them. For example, we should be equipped according to where we are going in Turkey. We are reading a book about that region." P10, P11

(c) Tour programs, "preparation of tour programs by people who do not know the region" (f=2), "trying to compress a large number of site visits in a short time so that the tour can be sold" (f=7), "agents do not consult the guide while preparing tour programs" (f=3), "inability to complete/incomplete tour programs that are more sales-oriented" (f=5), "over-inflated tour programs creating pressure" (f=4), "trying to apply the summer programs in the same way in winter" (f=1) is indicated. Below are the opinions chosen for the code of "trying to compress a large number of site visits in a short time so that the tour can be sold", which has the highest frequency for the sub-theme;

"Tour programs are mostly prepared by people who do not know the region, and even if it is not, trying to compress a large number of place visits in a short time in order to sell the tour is a factor that forces the guide and reduces his efficiency." K11.

"If the tour program is made by asking the guide on the agency side, there is no problem. When some agencies try to implement the program in April-May in October-November, of course, time problems arise.... It is the guide who manages the tour programs, so the guide should also be consulted." K1, K2, K3, K6.

"It has been observed from time to time that agencies aim to increase their sales by adding too many places in the tour program. This means that everything is incomplete or incomplete. Over-inflated schedules reduce productivity. Because there is always the pressure to get somewhere... Keeping the number of places to visit reasonable in the tour definitely increases the efficiency." K2, K3, K8, K11.

Table 1. Qualitative Findings on Professional Tourist Guides' Perceptions of Efficiency.

Codes	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	f	%
Sub-theme: Job satisfaction and job security													
Ability to work independently			√	√					√	√	√	5	45.4
The profession is not in the position it deserves in society	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	10	90.9
The profession does not provide a guaranteed future		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√	9	81.8
Giving you the chance to do something with the skills you have.		√			√	√						3	27.2
Difficulty of working conditions	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	11	100
Agency compliance					√						√	2	18.1
The region's readiness for tourism												3	27.2
Due to the short-term and irregular nature of the profession, different pursuits are sought.	√	√	√				√		√			5	45.4
Decreased love and desire for the profession in an insecure environment	√									√	√	3	27.2
Sub-theme: Group properties													
Trying to compress a large number of site visits into a short time so that the tour can be sold		√	√	√		√		√	√		√	7	63.6
Agents not consulting the guide while preparing tour programs	√	√	√									3	27.2
Inability to complete/incomplete tour programs, which are more sales-oriented		√			√	√	√	√				5	45.4

Overinflated tour schedules create pressure		√	√					√			√	4	36.3
Trying to apply the programs in the summer season in the same way in the winter season	√											1	9.09
Sub-theme: Professional cooperation													
Lack of transparent information sharing due to the fact that information is at the forefront in the sector	√							√	√	√		4	36.3
Joint sharing and assistance		√	√	√	√	√					√	7	63.6
Collaboration builds trust		√									√	2	18.1
Presence of an active communication network in the connected room	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	1	100
Increasing practical training	√											1	9.09
Meeting agency expectations		√		√		√		√			√	5	45.4

Source: proper elaboration form the empirical research.

4.2 Quantitative Results

Demographic characteristics of 387 professional tourist guides participating in the quantitative research are presented in Table 6. It is possible to say that the majority of the participants (72.87%) are male tourist guides. Similarly, it can be said that the number of guides registered to the Tourist Guiding Association in our country, according to gender, is mostly male guides, and there is a big difference (Tureb, 2021).

In their literature, Yılmaz and Köroğlu (2012, p. 635) stated in their study on tourist guides that the reason for this situation is that female guides choose the guiding profession less than men because of family reasons. In the profession of professional tourist guide, it is a profession group that women have difficulties due to the physical competence that can be listed as working conditions, flexible and intense working hours, the fact that Anatolian and similar tours take 10 days or more, staying away from home and social perception towards women.

Arslan and Şimşek (2018, p. 23), as a result of the qualitative research they conducted in Aydın province regarding the problems experienced by female tourist guides professionally, determined six categories and summarized them as follows; (a) social and family-related problems, (b) problems caused by colleagues and colleagues, (c) problems caused by travel agencies, (d) problems caused by the sector and the guidance profession, (e) problems caused by customers, (f) audit and training.

Table 2. Demographic Characteristics of the Participants.

Variables	N	%
Gender		
Woman	105	27.13
Man	282	72.87
Marital status		
Married	119	30.75
Single	268	69.25
Age		
18-30	58	14.98
31-40	165	42.64
41-50	135	34.88
51 and above	29	7.50
Working Status		
Affiliated to the Agency	109	28.17
Independent	278	71.83

Source: proper elaboration form the empirical research.

Table 3. Explanatory Factor Analysis of the 26-Item Scale.

Madde No	Factors					
	GABCompliance	Job Security	Group Requests	Tour Programs	Professional Cooperation	Job Satisfaction

When the marital status of professional tourist guides in Table 2 is analysed, the number of single (69.25%) tourist guides is found to be significantly higher. According to the age variable, the tourist guides participating in the study are mostly between the ages of 31-40 and 41-50. As a different finding, in a study on the motivations of tourist guides, Erkol Bayram (2017, p. 261) found that 74.6% of the tourist guides were men, 25.4% were women, 43.4% of the participants were 46 and over, 40 of them were between the ages of 31-45 and 16.6% were between the ages of 18-30; It was found that 68% were married and 32% were single.

Çakmak and Dinçer (2020, p. 3331), who conducted research on the crisis management skills of tourist guides, stated that 61.1% of the tourist guides were female guides and 38.9% were male guides, their age group was 31.6%. It turned out to be between the ages of 30-39. Mode (peak value) is the value with the highest frequency. In the table above, it has been obtained that professional tourist guides tend to self-employment with a mode class of 71.83% in terms of their working style.

Figure 4. Trace Chart of Factor Analysis.

Source: proper elaboration form the empirical research.

Item10	,712					
Item 6	,697					
Item 7	,656					
Item 12	,615					
Item 14	,590					
Item 8		,748				
Item 9		,737				
Item 25		,609				
Item 5		,571				
Item 11		,541				
Item 30		,484				
Item 17			,792			
Item 16			,748			
Item 18			,724			
Item 15			,585			
Item 21				,757		
Item 22				,739		
Item 23				,736		
Item 19				,544		
Item 27					,848	
Item 26					,807	
Item 28					,785	
Item 1						,729
Item 2						,712
Item 4						,617
Item 3						,594

Total variance explanation rate (%): 68,956 KMO: ,913 Bartlett Test of Sphericity: 6035,642 p: .000
Source: proper elaboration form the empirical research.

According to Table 3, because of the explanatory factor analysis of the scale items, it was determined that the items were collected in 6 factor dimensions most appropriately and the factor loadings of the items were between .48 and .84. Scale sub-dimensions, in connection with the theoretical model; Group-Agent-Region harmony, job security, group demands, tour programs, professional cooperation and job satisfaction. As a result of the analysis, four incompatible items were removed from the 30-item scale. In addition, in the factor analysis with 26 items, the Kaiser-Meyer Olkin (KMO) coefficient was .913 and the result of the Barlett Sphericity test was 6035,642; $p = ,000$ was found to be highly significant.

In Figure 4, in the trace diagram of factor analysis, it is understood that factor loads, and six-dimensional productivity scale are compatible. As a result of reducing the number of items in the scale to 26, the items were subjected

to reliability analysis again to determine internal consistency, and the reliability (Cronbach's Alpha) value of 26 items in total was found to be 0.934, a highly reliable scale. The reliability of the sub-dimensions was examined separately and presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Reliability Analysis of the empirical research.

Sub-Dimensions	Cronbach Alpha Values
Group-Agent-Region Compatibility	0.857478
Job Security	0.817916
Group Requests	0.840932
Tour Programs	0.838797
Professional Cooperation	0.882036
Job Satisfaction	0.759226
General	0.934469

Source: proper elaboration form the empirical research.

Table 5. Display of Expressions in the Sub-Dimensions of the 26-Item Scale.

Item No	Expressions	Sub-Dimension
Item 10	The educational/cultural level of the group affects my work efficiency.	Group-Agent-Region harmony
Item 6	Tourist guide-agent harmony is important in business efficiency.	
Item 7	The region's readiness for tourism has a positive impact on my work efficiency.	
Item 12	The intention of the group to join the tour affects my work efficiency.	
Item 14	Joint sharing with the group, ensuring harmony and acting together positively affect my work efficiency.	
Item 8	Since my job is short-term and irregular, I am in search of different things.	Job security
Item 9	In an insecure environment, the love and desire I feel for my profession is decreasing.	
Item 25	There is no transparent exchange of information among my colleagues, as information is prominent in the sector.	
Item 5	Difficult working conditions in my profession reduce my work efficiency.	
Item 11	The socio-economic status of the group affects my work efficiency.	
Item 30	The tourist guide who meets the expectations of the agency is efficient.	Group requests
Item 17	If I meet the expectations of the group, I will be an efficient tourist guide.	
Item 16	If I can't meet the group's needs, I'll be an ineffective tourist guide.	
Item 18	The group's satisfaction with the tour is only possible with an efficient tour guide.	Tour programs
Item15	I'll be a good tourist guide if I can control the group.	
Item 21	It increases my work efficiency if the agency consults me while preparing the tour programs.	
Item 22	The incomplete/incompleteness of the tour programs, which are more sales-oriented, reduces my work efficiency.	

Item No	Expressions	Sub-Dimension
Item 23	The pressure of over-inflated tour schedules affects my work efficiency.	
Item 19	The preparation of tour programs by people who do not know the region reduces my work efficiency.	
Item 27	Professional association provides trust, and this has a positive effect on work efficiency.	Professional Cooperation
Item 26	Joint sharing and assistance among my colleagues increases work efficiency.	
Item 28	Having an effective communication network in the room I am connected to increases my work efficiency.	
Item 1	Having the opportunity to work independently in my profession increases my work efficiency.	Job Satisfaction
Item 2	The fact that my profession is not in the position it deserves in the society reduces my work efficiency.	
Item 4	The fact that my profession does not provide a guaranteed future negatively affects my work efficiency.	
Item 3	My job gives me a chance to do something with the talents I have.	

Source: proper elaboration from the empirical research.

In the assumptions on which the questionnaires are based, it is accepted that the participant understands the questions as intended by the researcher, is voluntary, sincere, impartial, and rational. In this context, it can be interpreted that the items removed are not fully understood by some of the participants, or that the participants answer these questions based on the feeling that they are being measured, and that they act with the idea of me.

Similarly, it can be evaluated that the words homogeneous and heterogeneous in item 13 cannot be fully perceived by tourist guides, even if expert opinion is taken, and should be included in the jargon phrases group. Despite the fact that we cannot make a firm judgment regarding all of these, this and related issues are among the subjects covered in survey research for quantitative studies. The questionnaires' underlying presumptions were accepted for this investigation, and the essential items were eliminated.

4.3 Discussion of the Data

Since there is no efficiency perception scale for professional tourist guides in the literature, in the study prepared to fill the gap in this area, firstly, a literature review and a document review for scale development were made. Since some word-meaning errors will occur in adapting and using a scale from a foreign culture, it has been seen that it is more appropriate to develop a local and original scale, and for this, the mixed method has been adopted as the research method that overlaps with the purpose of the research. Among the mixed method designs, the exploratory sequential design was preferred.

This mixed method design is called sequential design by Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2014) and preparing the qualitative part first and then the quantitative part, and it is called exploratory sequential design by Creswell (2005). In addition, within this design, equal status was preferred as the paradigm emphasis of Christensen, Johnson, and Turner (2014). The reason why equal status is preferred is that the quantity or quality is not more dominant, it is kept equal. The basis of the study is the phenomenology design, as it reveals the perceptions of individuals (tourist guides) about a phenomenon (efficiency) and the meanings they attribute to them, from qualitative research designs.

Phenomenology is an appropriate research design for studies that aim to investigate phenomena that are not unfamiliar to us, but whose concept we cannot clearly understand (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2016, p. 69). In the research, the ethical approach, which is concerned with the interpretation of aspects of another culture by the observers,

that is, the researchers, using their own categories, and the emic approach, which tries to understand a particular culture on the basis of its own references, were used.

Professional tourist guides participating in the research primarily characterized an efficient tourist guide as customer-oriented, empathetic, knowledgeable about the tour area, having a general culture, loving his job, and knowing people. In this respect, in order for a tourist guide to be efficient, it is necessary to have good human relations and effective communication skills apart from knowledge. Professional tourist guide is also a leader in terms of management, he is the locomotive of the group.

Because it strives for people gathered for a specific purpose to achieve this goal. At the same time, a professional tourist guide is a tourist-tourist, a mediator who resolves tourist-local disputes. The codes determined within the framework of the answers given by the 11 nationally active professional tourist guides participating in the qualitative research were divided into 6 sub-themes and named as job satisfaction and job security, group characteristics, tour programs and professional cooperation.

As a result of the interviews, professional tourist guides stated that there is an effective communication network in the room they are connected to, and they are always informed in the digital environment, via mobile or e-mail, as a factor that reduces their productivity, especially job security problems, as a factor that increases their productivity.

They also stated that exaggerated programs designed to visit too many places in a short time in order to make more profit reduce their efficiency and this situation creates stress for them. In such a case, in order to ensure efficiency, it would be much more appropriate to consult the professional tourist guide who will go on the tour while preparing the tour program, or to give importance to the feedback of the professional tourist guides about the tour plan after the tour.

5 CONCLUSIONS

As a result of the literature review, there are many studies attributed to the professional tourist guide profession. It is possible to say that the status exists. According to Holloway (1981), courier, companion, missionary, messenger, leader, guardian angel, disciplinarian-commander; According to Tang (1989), travel manager, group consultant, actor, tour manager, tour guide, tour companion, tour leader; Pond (1993), tour manager, tour companion, tour leader, tour guide, city guide.

This the peacock metaphor of the professional tourist guide, who is welcomed with more than one status in terms

of it was thought by the researcher to resemble a bird. The peacock has a wide the color scale is like a tourist guide identified with different statuses. Moreover

According to Salt (2010), the peacock holds the throne in Hindu and Tibetan traditions. While symbolizing it, it can be associated with the guide's leadership, consultancy and mentoring. In addition, since its tail feathers are multi-eyed, it can literally cover the earth. While it symbolizes that you understand and do not miss anything, it is also professional in a similar way.

The tourist guide is also a good scholar and careful commentator. In the perception of an efficient tourist guide, the participants first described an efficient tourist guide as being customer-oriented, empathetic, well-informed about the tour area, having a general culture, loving his job, and knowing people.

On the other hand, they also stated that the lack of these features or vice versa is an inefficient tourist guide. Some professional tourist guides concentrate on general understanding and knowledge, while others concentrate on customer-focused sales, in terms of providing effective professional tourist guidance. In this context, thinking of the profession as sales-oriented rather than knowledge also changes today's expectation of the profession.

As a result of a study on the importance of a tour guide in the tourist experience, it has been revealed that travel agency managers understand the important role of a tour guide in the success of their business, and this professional must have certain skills and characteristics in order to fulfill his role in a way that allows tourists to have a different and high-quality experience in the destination (Panzini et. al, 2017).

Canani (1999) showed the importance of practicing the tourist guiding profession in Brazil as an element that ensures quality in tourist services. It has highlighted the need for agencies to guide and accompany tourists in order to present the image of the places visited and the services offered, providing the visitor with moments of leisure and satisfaction. Scale development study on professional tourist guides in the national literature. It appears to be almost non-existent. This research examines the work of professional tourist guides.

To explore their perceptions on productivity and to reveal the factors affecting their work productivity. This is a scale development study with the aim of the research, exploratory sequential mixed the method was adopted and the idea was to create an original and local scale. Therefore, it is important to fill such a gap in the national literature and to provide professional tourist resources. In order to increase research in the field of scale development for guides to contribute and to work on efficiency in professional tourist guides. This research is considered important in order to guide researchers who want to study it.

As a result of a study conducted by Pimentel (2017), if we want to achieve a broader and effective management system for tourist destinations, it is necessary to analyze how the area is structured, who the actors are, what their locations are, and what their tendencies to act in some way are. Based on this, tourist guides are an important actor in the tourism sector. But the studies on tourist guides in the field of tourism literature are not enough. The study focusing on the field of tourist guidance will be a guide for researchers working in this field. Since the research took place in Turkey, it was

conducted from the point of view of Turkish tourist guides. It can be adapted to tourist guides from different nationalities or a comparison between nationalities can be made.

This study fills the gap in the literature in three ways. This study first of all proposes a scale to measure the perceptions of tourist guides towards efficiency. Secondly, this article responds to the call to develop a tool for evaluating the effectiveness of guidance. Finally, the efficiency dimensions of tour guidance obtained from the results of this study can help tour leaders to perform at their best.

The study has both theoretical and practical contributions. The subject is on tourist guides who have little work in the literature. The discovery of the factors affecting the efficiency of tourist guides has made the subject even more original. The resulting scale development is work. The scale is original, revealed by qualitative and quantitative methods. In terms of its practical contribution, the study has divided tourist guides into two in terms of efficiency.

Egypt, which makes the most tour sales of productive tourists? Is he a person with a general culture who describes the fertile tourist country in the most beautiful way? Based on this study, what is important for travel agencies is the sale of tours, and for the country, it is an efficient tourist guide that best introduces the country. The expectations of the country and the tourism sector from the tourist guide are too high. The tourist guide should meet these expectations.

5.1 Contribution to Mixed Methods Research

This study contributes to the mixed method field of research in the field of social sciences. In the study presented specifically for the field of tourism, the efficiency of both tourist guides was studied in depth. Findings were extracted both from the outside and from the inside as an eye. . Mixed-method research will be guiding in terms of revealing both international dimensions and global diffusion by using various methods with people from different regions or social levels.

Examples of this will contribute to the mixed method and will help the researcher to understand cultural, class and ethnic differences not only within and between societies. The fact that the sources written on this subject and the increase in studies on this subject also strengthen the unity of the focus of more solidly based mixed method research on the ongoing method. The issue of efficiency will not lose its relevance and it will be a subject area that humanity will always work on. Similar work can be adapted for different nationalities or different professional groups.

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CRedit author statement

Term	Definition	Author 1	Author 2
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	x	x
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	x	
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	x	
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	x	x
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	x	x
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	x	x
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	x	x
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	x	x
Writing - Original Draft	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation)	x	x
Writing - Review & Editing	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre-or post-publication stages	x	x
Visualization	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/ data presentation	x	x
Supervision	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team		x
Project administration	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution		x
Funding acquisition	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication	x	x

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